

Comparative study of Regular Home Loan provided by State Bank of India and Life Insurance co-operation

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Abstract -

Today's era is an era of competition. In order to surviving in this competitive era, it is important to satisfy the customers. The needs of the customers are constantly changing and these needs to be must complete for retained the customers. In this research paper is presented a comparative study of regular Home Loan provided by the State Bank of India and Life Insurance co-operation. The Life Insurance Corporation of India is the source of the LIC Housing Finance Trust. But State Bank is recognized as the top bank for its credit facilities. You must still make a choice when considering a home loan even though you have the option of both. But first, you must know which better option is. Therefore Interest rate, total disbursement, repayment period and process fees, etc. This factor is examined in this research paper and is presented an analysis regarding which organization can provide affordable a regular home loan to the consumer.

Key Words - State Bank of India, Life Insurance Co-corporation, Home loan, Interest Rate, disbursement, comparison

Introduction:

Everyone wants to own a house, but it is not so easy to dream of a house. Most of the people have to put their dreams on hold just because of lack of money. If you also want to buy a house, you must have money for it. To resolve this activity, government provides housing finance loan facility for every person at lower interest rate. Many banks are providing home loans whether commercial banks or financial institutions to the people who want to have a home. State Bank of India (SBI) is an Indian multinational public sector bank and financial services statutory body headquartered in Mumbai, Maharashtra. SBI is the 48th largest bank in the world by total assets and India's largest government sector bank that provides banking and financial services. Similarly, Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC) is an Indian

multinational public sector life insurance company headquartered in Mumbai. It is India's largest insurance company. It is under the ownership of Government of India and administrative control of the Ministry of Finance.

Life Insurance co-operation provides Insurance services at the same time other services are also provided. State Bank of India and Life Insurance Corporation both institutions provide regular home loan. In this research paper presented comparative study of regular Home Loan between State Bank of India and Life Insurance Cooperation. In this study examines regular home Loan interest rate, total disbursement, repayment period, and process fee. Therefore Presented Last 5 year's regular home loan details about State Bank of India and Life Insurance co-operation are given as below.

Dia.1.1 Last 5 years regular Home Loan details of State Bank of India

Year	Interest Rate	Loan Amt	Loan Tenure	Processed Fees
2018-2019	8.95%	70% Property value	Up to 30 Years	-
2019-2020	7.30%	70% Property value	Up to 30 Years	0.35% of Loan Amt
2020-2021	7.55%	70% Property value	Up to 30 Years	0.35% -1% of Loan Amt
2021-2022	9.40%	80% Property value	Up to 30 Years	1% of Loan Amt
2022-2023	10.10%	80% Property value	Up to 30 Years	1% of Loan Amt

- Ref-** 1) <https://sbi.co.in/web/interest-rates/interest-rates/base-rate-historical-data>
2) Published report

Dia.1.2 Last 5 years regular Home Loan details of Life Insurance co-operation

Year	Interest Rate	Loan Amt	Loan Tenure	Processed Fees
2018-2019	8.35%	30 lakh to 20 corer	Up to 30 Yeas(Salaried Person) Up to 25 Years(Self Employed)	₹10,000+GST
2019-2020	8%	30 lakh to 18 corer	Up to 30 Yeas(Salaried Person) Up to 25 Years(Self Employed)	₹10,000+GST
2020-2021	6.66%	30 lakh to 16crore	Up to 30 Yeas(Salaried Person) Up to 25 Years(Self Employed)	₹12,000+GST
2021-2022	8.%	30 lakh to 16 corer	Up to 30 Yeas(Salaried Person) Up to 25 Years(Self Employed)	₹10,000+GST
2022-2023	8.65%	1 lakh to 15 corer	Up to 30 Yeas(Salaried Person) Up to 25 Years(Self Employed)	0% - 0.50% +GST

Ref- 1) <https://www.bankbazaar.com/lic-home-loan.html>

2) LIC information manual

The above details was clear that there is a comparatively difference in interest rate, loan amount, repayment period and procedure fee of regular home loan provided by State Bank of India and Life Insurance Corporation of India. Looking at the above data, the regular Home Loan interest rate of State Bank of India has increased during the 5 year period 2018-2023. But State Bank of India

relaxation in interest rates was given due to Covide Period during 2019-21. Similarly, the interest rate of regular home loan of Life Insurance Corporation of India has not increased much. The interest rate is high of the State Bank of India as compared to Life Insurance Corporation. But processes fee is less than Life Insurance Corporation.

1.3 Comparison between SBI and LIC Regular Home Loan Interest Rate

Ref -1) <https://sbi.co.in/web/interest-rates/interest-rates/base-rate-historical-data>

2) LIC Information manual.

The regular home loan interest rates provided by State Bank of India and Life Insurance Corporation of India Comparatively LIC's home loan interest rate is lower than SBI's Home Loan Interest Rate. So LIC's Regular Home Loan Interest

Rate is affordable to the customer as compared to SBI and LIC lend home loan in huge amount than SBI. The Disbursement details of Regular Home Loan Provided by SBI and LIC in the last 5 years is presented as follows.

1.4 Regular Home Loan Disbursement of SBI and LIC

Year	Disbursement Regular Home Loan	
	SBI (Crore)	LIC (Crore)
2018-2019	3.41 Crore	49 Crore
2019-2020	4.00 Crore	53 Crore
2020-2021	4.56 Crore	46 Crore
2021-2022	5.04 Crore	55 Crore
2022-2023	5.62 Crore	72 Crore

In the disbursement of regular home loan provided by State Bank of India and Life insurance Corporation 2018 and 2023 during period LIC

provide large amount of regular home loan as compared to the State Bank of India. Because SBI provide different type of financial services so State

Bank of India has limitation. And LIC provide limited services like mutual fund, home loan, ulip, etc. Therefore LIC lend huge amount for home loan.

Data and Methodology:

Secondary and primary sources of data have been used for the research paper study it includes visits, published reports, brochures, newspapers, website information etc. in this sources collect information and data for studied.

Result and discussion:

According to my study SBI Bank and LIC have widest range of home loan products and maximum people prefer fixed rates on home loans. According to my research the rate of interest of LIC is less than SBI Bank. People get knowledge about home loans from television, internet, Newspaper, Media or families and friends. In the presented research State Bank of India and Life insurance Corporation has helped the customers to fulfill their dream of purchase a smart home through mass distribution of home loan. But LIC's home loan interest rates are affordable to the customers as compared to the SBI. Because recently SBI home loan interest rate is 9.50% and LIC home loan interest rate is 8.65%.

Conclusion:

It is seen that the interest rate of SBI and LIC home loan has been change during the period of 2018 - 2023 years. And also there is a discrepancy between repayment period and procedure. On the basis of collected data, it is being concluded that customers are satisfied by LIC regular home loan because LIC rate of interest is lower as compare to the State Bank of India. The Conclusion is that LIC's home loan interest rate is affordable to consumers as compared to the SBI. But process fees high as compared to the State Bank of India. As per the details comparing the SBI and LIC home loan disbursement during the last five years period 2018-2023, LIC has disbursed large amount of home loan as compared to the SBI. On the basis of collected data, the demand of regular home loan increasingly day by day.

Reference:

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